

A Study on Relationship between Achievement Motivation and Academic Achievement in English among High School Students

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Achievement - Achievement imagery in fantasy takes the form of thoughts about performing some task well, of sometimes being blocked, of trying various means of achieving, and of experiencing joy or sadness contingent upon the outcome of the effort. The particular diagnostic signs of achievement motivation were identified by experimental fact. The results of validating experiments have been replicated in other social groups and societies. Together these experimental findings specify what is counted in an imaginative protocol to yield the n Achievement source, an assessment of the strength of achievement motivation.

In this paper the following points to be addressed in more details for achievement motivation and academic achievements.

1. Review of literature
2. Analysis and data collection
3. Results
4. Conclusion

Review of Literature

Jena, R. K. (2019) studied across business, industry, government and other areas of human endeavor, vast amounts of data are being accumulated and processed to

ABSTRACT

The aim of this longitudinal study was to Relationship between Achievement Motivation and Academic Achievement in English among High School Students. A sample of 300 students participated in the study. Results of structural equation modeling showed that mastery goals (approach and avoidance) were indirect predictors of both behavioral and cognitive engagement through seeking help from teachers. Performance goals (avoidance, but not approach orientation) were associated with cognitive engagement through help-seeking behaviors. Overall, these results suggest that achievement goals are key drivers of changes in academic engagement in early high school and that their contribution is explained by seeking help from teachers. Practical implications, limitations, and future research directions are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Achievement Motivation - also referred to as the need for achievement, is an important determinant of aspiration, effort, and persistence when an individual expects his performance will be evaluated in relation to some standard of excellence. Such behavior is called achievement-oriented. Motivation - to achieve is instigates when an individual knows that he is responsible for the outcome of some venture, when he anticipates explicit knowledge of results that will define his success or failure, and when there is some degree of risk, i.e., some uncertainty about the outcome of his effort. The goal of achievement oriented activity is to succeed, to perform well in relation to a standard of excellence or in comparison with others who are competitors.

develop understanding of people's activities, and to optimize organizational processes and outputs. Business analytic related technologies are playing major roles in providing useful insights from vast amount of data..

Rani, S. (2019) discussed the poor academic achievement in school can be the result of differences between child factors and environment.

Gupta, A. (2019) behavior of the learner in teaching learning situation besides being influenced by several psycho-social factors is also influenced by the structure and dynamics of his instructional group.

Jain, D., Tiwari, G. K., & Awasthi, I. (2018). attempted to examine the impacts of academic locus of control and metacognitive awareness on the academic adjustment of the student participants.

Yadava, S., & Yadava, A. (2018) academic achievement represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in school, college, and university.

Sharma, H. L. (2018) The present study was planned to study the correlation among Cognitive Styles, Achievement

Motivation and Academic Achievement using Multimedia and Traditional Instructional Strategies.

Variables of the Study

In research, this term refers to the measurable characteristics, qualities, traits or attributes of a particular individual, object or situation being studied. Nurses use the term variable whether they are conducting, reading or using results of qualitative or quantitative research. Researchers often refer to variable by the terms dependent or independent. Dependent variable represent outcomes of interest and they are affect by independent (i.e predictor) variables. In this study, the investigator follows independent variable and dependent variables.

An independent variable is a variable that is expected to influence the dependent variables. Its value may be changed or altered, which is independent of any other variables. Also the following demographic variables were used as independent variables.

- Gender (Male/Female)
- Medium of Study (Tamil/English)
- Type of School (Government/Private)
- Parents Education (Educated/Uneducated)
- Locality of the School (Urban/Rural)

Sampling Techniques

The sample which was collected from various schools located in and around Coimbatore is shown as below.

TABLE 1
LIST OF SCHOOLS USED FOR DATA COLLECTION

S.No	Name of the schools	Number of students
1	Infant Jesus Matriculation Higher Secondary School, Tiruppur	42
2	Government Higher secondary School, Tiruppur	53
3	Michael Job Matriculation Higher Secondary School, Suler	45
4	Government Boys Higher secondary School, Suler	56
5	Government Girls Higher secondary School, Suler	52
6	Sri Ramaswamy Naidu Vidyalayam Higher Secondary School, Suler	52
Total		300

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Hypotheses:1

TABLE 3
Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Gender.

S.No	Gender	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Male	166	1.5963	284	2.9784	0.0031	Reject
2	Female	134	1.4253				

The Table 3 shows the mean score difference in significant study relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Gender (Male/Female).The calculated t value is statistically less value, a significance at 0.05 to 0.0031 levels and hence the hypotheses 1 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean score difference in significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Gender.

TABLE 2

DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLES BASED ON VARIABLES

S.No	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1	Gender	Male	166	55	300
		Female	134	45	
2	Medium of Study	Tamil	213	71	300
		English	87	29	
3	Type of School	Government	161	54	300
		Private	139	46	
4	Parents Education	Educated	116	39	300
		Uneducated	184	61	
5	School Locality	Rural	95	32	300
		Urban	205	68	

Research Tool

Tool become another major consideration in an education research. The instrument employed for the collection of data required for the study of any problem is called tool. "Tool employ distinction way of describing and qualifying the data" the important tools of educational research include interview schedule, questionnaire, observation, rating scale, achievement test, proficiency test, psychological tests and sociogram.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Gender.
2. There is no significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Medium of study.
3. There is no significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Type of school.
4. There is no significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their parent's education.
5. There is no significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Locality.
6. There is no significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their parents' income.
7. There is no significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Parents employment.

CHART 1
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH BASED ON THEIR GENDER

Hypotheses:2

TABLE 4
Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Medium of study.

S.No	Gender	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Tamil	213	1.4131	158	-0.5541	0.5802	Reject
2	English	87	1.4482				

CHART 2
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH BASED ON THEIR MEDIUM OF STUDY

Hypotheses:3

TABLE 5
Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Type of School.

S.No	Locality	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Government	161	1.5155	292	-0.2904	0.7717	Accept
2	Private	139	1.5324				

CHART 3
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF SCHOOL

Hypotheses: 4

TABLE 6

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Parents Education

S.No	Locality	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Educated	116	1.4741	245	-0.5265	0.5990	Accept
2	Uneducated	184	1.5054				

CHART 4

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH BASED ON THEIR PARENTS EDUCATION

Hypotheses: 5

TABLE 7

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Locality.

S.No	Locality	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Rural	95	1.5053	183	0.2801	0.7797	Accept
2	Urban	205	1.4878				

CHART 5

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH BASED ON THEIR LOCALITY

TABLE 8

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Parent income.

S.No	Parent Income	N	Mean	Variance	df	t-Value	Result
1	More than 100000	120	1.9750	3.5540	298	2.1	S
2	Less than 100000	180	1.6056	0.2402			

CHART 6

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH BASED ON THEIR PARENTS' INCOME

TABLE 9

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English based on their Parents' employment.

S.No	Parents' employment	N	Mean	df	t-Value	Result
1	Self Employed	116	1.5368	298	0.02	NS
2	Salaried	184	1.5380			

CHART 7

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH BASED ON THEIR PARENTS' EMPLOYMENT

Summary of the Findings

- A study on high school students' relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English was studied and the findings reveal that there is a **significant** difference between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English with respect to **Gender and Parents' income**.
- A study on high school students' relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English was studied and the findings reveal that there is **no significant** difference between achievement motivation and academic achievement in English with respect to **Medium of study, Type of school, Parent's Education, Locality and Parents' Employment**

Conclusion

There is also some evidence to suggest that perceptions of the classroom academic motivation may exert a direct effect on outcome measures as well. The use of multilevel data analysis procedures enables researchers to test the predictive influence of classroom academic motivations at both the individual and classroom levels. In this research, learning environments may be characterized as having either a greater mastery or performance focus (or a simultaneous focus on both mastery and performance) when students' perceptions of the academic motivation are aggregated to the classroom or school level.

Evidence to date indicates that approximately 5% to 35% of the variation in students' academic motivation perceptions is related to classroom differences. When added to the analyses, mean perceptions of the classroom academic motivation explain variance in some outcome measures not explained by individual perceptions of classroom academic motivations, personal achievement goals, or student background characteristics.

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PERSONAL DATA SHEET**APPENDICES: PROFORMA FOR BASIC DATA**

Name of the student :
 Name of the school :
 Gender :
 Medium of Study :
 Type of School :
 Parents Education :
 Locality :

INSTRUCTIONS

- There are some statement below. Each statement is followed by multiple choice i.e Yes,/No.
- Read each Statement carefully.
- After reading each statement mark your response in the appropriate column putting a tick mark.

S.No	Questionnaire	Yes	No
1	I like learning English.		
2	I will persist when facing difficulties in English learning		
3	I like listening to English speech		
4	I like reading English articles		
5	I feel more confident in English learning compared with my classmates		
6	I work on my English assignments according to a planned schedule		
7	I study English diligently for potential development in the future		
8	In order to know the recent development in my major, I study English diligently		
9	English is a very important tool for communication so I study it diligently		
10	In order to get an ideal job in the future I study English diligently		
11	English learning takes great advantage on the future work		
12	I treat English examination as an evaluation of what I have learned about English.		
13	I like English movies.		
14	I am excited when I have accomplished a difficult task in English learning.		
15	I can finish my English homework actively		
16	1) I study English hard for the praise of the teacher.		
17	My teacher helps me to improve my English language		
18	My teachers always give lot of new words to understand English.		
19	My teachers encourage me to participate in English competitions		
20	I like teachers who have some sense of humour		
21	My teacher helps me in understanding the difficult English lessons		
22	My teacher ask me to read English newspaper daily		